

CLASSIFICATION OF ECONOMIC-GEOGRAPHICAL AND SOCIO-ECONOMIC FACTORS IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF TOURISM

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ABSTRACT

This article describes the classification of economic-geographical and socio-economic factors in the development of regional tourism, as well as the essence of the concept of "tourist services market" in systematic approaches.

The initial document for setting specific goals for the development of the regional tourism development strategy is the concept. Summarized, it defines the scope, rates, proportions and main directions of the socio-economic development of the region, its separate structural and functional parts and problem areas, as well as measures aimed at increasing the efficiency of production management. The system of events is based on a general basis, methods of eliminating regional and intersectoral disparities are given, and the level of service to tourists is justified. Figure 1.

On the basis of the concept of optimal regulation of regional tourism development, sectoral and regional programs, targeted complex documents are developed, in which detailed and clearly based aspects, as well as coordination of problematic issues, are raised to the concept level, and this concept is considered a methodology for regulating regional tourism development, which consists of four blocks and three equal consists of level aspects. The correct choice of strategy allows to realize the potential of economic development of touristic resources and thereby ensure effective development of regions in market conditions. In the process of developing the strategy, the role, role and functions of the regions are defined in the context of the implementation of the concept of administrative reforms, the strategic priorities of the development of the region in the changing economic conditions are determined, and the economic, financial and organizational mechanisms of the implementation of the strategy in the new institutional conditions are established.

Figure 1. Methodical concession for optimal regulation of regional tourism development

In order to develop a method of optimal regulation of regional tourism development, it is necessary to pay attention to specific events first. It is necessary to discuss the problems, causes and countermeasures of regional tourism development regulation and reach a consensus on the meaning of the concept of regulation. Due to the mobility of tourism activities and the intangible nature of tourism products, it is important to develop a conceptual model of regulation and direct application of existing research results to regulate the development of regional tourism. In the optimal regulation of tourism in the region, strategic planning for development, attracting investments, marketing methods, providing new types of services for various forms of business in the region, and forming incentives aimed at creating jobs are used, and with the help of these methods, it is necessary to classify several factors for the development of tourism. Table 1 .

Table 1

Classification of economic-geographic and socio-economic factors in the development of regional tourism

No	Classification factors	The content of the essence
1	Socio-economic factors	It affects development strategy, technology, investment, innovation, demography (labor resources), ecology, infrastructure and others.
2	Factors of tourism resources	Attracting special raw materials to production processes affects the formation of new production networks.
3	Strategic factors	It helps to develop long-term forecasts of the national economy and to determine ways to increase the competitiveness of regions.
4	Technological factors	It provides an opportunity to organize production based on new high technologies and develop a scientific educational complex.
5	Investment Factors	Creating an attractive investment climate, expanding investment sources, attracting foreign direct investment.
6	Innovation factors	The development of the regional innovation system, as well as the placement of enterprises, will help to form institutions for the commercialization of innovations.
7	Transport factor	Mineral raw materials, fuel and energy, natural and climatic conditions, etc.
8	Environmental factors	Placement of production forces based on ecological situation and environmental safety requirements.
9	Agglomeration factors	Development of large and medium-sized cities, provision of socio-economic development in connection with issues of urbanization.

Thus, supporters of the integrated approach emphasize the need to involve many sectors of the economy in creating an integrated tourism product, and thus emphasize the importance of the interaction of the participating entities.

The existence of a wide range of definitions within each approach encourages analytical processing of their terminological apparatus. Summarizing the variety of definitions within the framework of the systemic approach allows to interpret the market of tourist services as a system of global economic relations, as a socio-economic system, as a multi-level system of relations between market entities. a system of internal and external relations, a finite variety of functional elements and the relations between them, as a multi-dimensional, multi-structural and multi-level system is formed in Table 2.

Table 2.

Interpretation of the essence of the concept of "tourist services market" based on a systematic approach

Authors	Interpretation of essence
1	2
SP Grabovenskaya¹	A system of world economic relations in which the process of converting tourist and excursion services into cash and reverse conversion of money into tourist and excursion services is carried out.
AA Lyubitseva²	The system is multi-dimensional, multi-structured and multi-level, and works according to the law of balancing demand and supply, as a result of which the need to coordinate the effective demand and supply of economic and natural-material forms in time and space is objectively reproduced. based on fluctuations in tourism product production and use
AA Komlichenko, NV Rotan³	A system of socio-economic relations that allows attracting natural recreational and cultural-historical heritage resources to the sphere of economic values
AP Yuriev⁴	A system of internal and external relations, where the process of converting tourist and excursion services into money and vice versa, money into tourist and excursion services is carried out
A. Kirillova⁵	An open socio-economic system with a high level of self-regulation, the basis of which is relations related to the production, sale and consumption of tourist services or a complex tourist product in a certain area, and a criterion for determining regional tourism. the market is the place of purchase of the tourist package and the consumption of tourist services included in it

At the same time, the central place of the systematic approach is occupied by the thesis that the starting point of the formation and development of the economic system of the tourist services market is the satisfaction of tourism needs, which is the basis of the demand for tourist products and tourist services. services and meeting this demand, in turn, is carried out through system offers in the market.

Taking into account the above, the analysis of theoretical developments made it possible to systematize theoretical approaches to the segmentation and classification of the tourist services market and to determine the most scientifically based comprehensive approach to the classification of tourist markets, distinguishing two important criteria. Thus, according to the ratio of supply and demand, divide the consumer market and the producer market, each of

¹Grabovenskaya S.P. Analiz i struktur rynka turistichekikh uslug v Ukraine / S.P. Grabovenskaya // Nauchnyi vestnik Poltavskogo universiteta ekonomiki i tovgovli. 2013. No. 1 (56). S. 226-234.

²Lyubitseva A.A. Rynok turistichekikh uslug (geoprostranstvennye aspekty) / A.A. Lyubitseva. - M.: Altpres, 2002. - 436 p

³Komlichenko A.A. Formirovanie i otsenka ekonomicheskogo potentsiala turistichekoy otrasli regiona / A.A. Komlichenko, N.V. Rotan // Vestnik Odesskogo natsionalnogo universiteta. Series: Economics - 2014. T-19, Vyp. 2 (4). S. 178-182.

⁴Yurev A.P. Safety and security in tourism. - Donetsk: DITB, 2001. - 100 p

⁵Kirillova A. Marketing na rynke turistichekikh uslug / A. Kirillova // Marketing v Ukraine. 2009. - #3. - S. 57-59.

them into separate segments (consumer market segments and producer market segments), tourist mesoregions (subregions), national. tourist markets, local markets. It is appropriate to use the following criteria when defining consumer market segments: socio-economic (social affiliation, income level, profession, type of activity); demographic (age, gender, marital status) psychological behavior (type of person that determines lifestyle, interests, motivation for traveling, level of readiness to perceive the product, loyalty to the tourist product or company). When determining the segments of the producer market, it is necessary to take into account all the entities of the market of tourist services participating in the creation of an integrated tourist product and providing services to tourists.

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